

THE ASSESSMENT OF CHINESE COMMERCIAL DIPLOMACY AND INVESTMENT IN AFRICA: NIGERIA CASE STUDY

Abdullahi Hussein Aden

Master Student, Foreign Trade Institute, Department of Commercial Diplomacy,
Istanbul Ticaret University, Istanbul, Turkey
aden7780@hotmail.com

Publication History

Manuscript Reference No: IJIRIS/RS/Vol.07/Issue06/JLIS10082

Received: 28, June 2020

Accepted: 28, July 2020

Published Online: 31, July 2020

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.26562/ijiris.2020.v0706.001>

Citation: Abdullahi (2020). The Assessment of Chinese Commercial Diplomacy and investment in Africa: Nigeria Case Study. IJIRIS: International Journal of Innovative Research in Information Security, Volume VII, 58-68.

Peer-review: Double-blind Peer-reviewed

Editor: Dr.A.Arul L.S, Chief Editor, IJIRIS, AM Publications, India

Copyright: ©2020 This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License; Which Permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited

Abstract: This paper investigates Chinese Commercial Diplomacy and investment in Nigeria. The paper shows that Commercial Diplomacy is a movement led by state delegates with political status in perspective on business advancement between a home and a host nation. The study employed qualitative research techniques whereby none of the present literature focuses on validating the findings quantitatively. The findings of the study revealed that China-Africa trade 2018 was \$185 bn, up from \$155 bn in 2017. In 2018, the biggest exporter to China from Africa was Angola, trailed by South Africa and the Republic of Congo, South Africa was the biggest purchaser of Chinese merchandise, trailed by Nigeria and Egypt. China's FDI in Africa is firmly connected to trade and improvement help. FDI has expanded in the course of recent years couple with expanded Sino-African trade, in spite of the fact that China's FDI to Africa stays minor as far as China's all out outward FDI flows (0.2% in 1991 and 5.9% in 2007) and all out FDI got by Africa from the remainder of the world (3% in 2007). The study concludes that Nigeria-China bilateral trade Nigeria-China two-sided trade has stayed low particularly before the consenting to two-sided trade arrangement. The study recommends that China needs to adjust its policies to assuage concerns of Nigeria and put the Sino-African relationship on a more balanced footing and legislature should attempt to draw in remote ventures from China to segments.

Keywords: FDI, Commercial Diplomacy (CDC), Export, Trade

I. INTRODUCTION

Historically, Commercial diplomatic activities can be dated back to the Roman Empire whereby Diplomatic missions have long been used as a tool to improve relations to other states around the world (Berridge, 2002). Today, commercial diplomacy activities, is a common behavior by developed countries (Kostecki and Naray, 2007). There is an increasing focus on commercial diplomacy, which can be related to the global economic stagnation and the decreasing growth many countries experience domestically (Justinek, 2012). Diplomatic activities may occur on the global level (respective, district or multilateral) or inside the host state (for instance, relations with government divisions, government employees, parliament, NGOs, business associations, partnerships, etc). Business discretion is a taxpayer driven organization to the business network, which focuses on the improvement of social advantageous worldwide undertakings. In some countries, commercial diplomacy has become a core part of the overall diplomatic corps, and it targets empowering business development. It focuses on a progression of activities so as to advance and encourage universal business. These exercises have been distinguished and ordered by various researchers. Naray recognizes six sorts of activities: Intelligence, Communication, referral, advocacy, co-ordination and logistics (Gray, Julia and Philip Potter. 2015). The 2018 Beijing Forum on China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) summit was the mark occasion that decided China's needs toward Africa for the following three years.

Veering off from its convention of multiplying or significantly increasing its money related promises, China's dedication continued as before as in 2015, \$60 billion. In light of its volume and organization, China's responsibility stays solid, yet seems, by all accounts, to be more mindful and ascertaining than its past promises (Biggeri, & Sanfilippo, 2015). The concessionality of the Chinese financing is being directed, while China has become unmistakably increasingly centered on the business and feasibility perspectives. From the conventional model of "assets for foundation," China gives off an impression of being transforming toward the following stage: value venture by a progressively various gathering of financial specialists upheld by state advancement fund. In the meantime, Africa despite everything has significant getting up to speed to do to acquire Chinese speculation and to enhance its trade relations with China (Jandhyala, Srividya and Robert Weiner. 2014). For sure, what China offers Africa is certifiably not an unlimited free pass and an ensured outcome. Rather, Beijing offers Africa the chance to accelerate its financial improvement dependent on the framework China creates, to use the innovations, business, and market openings China makes, and to animate the craving and rivalry for development through market-based as opposed to help based methodology. The Chinese financing is neither free nor unselfish. In any case, that isn't the point. China's interest in Africa is still at the beginning times contrasted and that of key European nations that have a provincial past in Africa, particularly France and the UK. It is mentionable that the FDI stocks sourced separately from the UK and France into Africa are each still bigger than the stock sourced from China (Lin, & Farrell, 2013).

1. Commercial Diplomacy

1.1 Definition of Commercial Diplomacy

Commercial Diplomacy is diplomacy that focuses on development of business between two countries.¹ Commercial diplomacy is often confused with economic diplomacy² and other types of diplomacy such as trade diplomacy and financial diplomacy.³ It aims at generating commercial gains in the form of trade and inward and outward investment by means of business and entrepreneurship promotion and facilitation activities in the host country.⁴ It targets producing business gains as trade and internal and outward venture by methods for business and enterprise advancement and assistance exercises in the host nation.⁵ Commercial Diplomacy is sought after with the objective of increasing monetary dependability, welfare, or upper hand.⁶ In writing the ideas of economic diplomacy and business strategy are frequently utilized reciprocally. It underscores the administration's job, being characterized as "a taxpayer supported organization to the business network, which focuses on the improvement of socially useful universal undertakings". Commercial Diplomacy therefore incorporates "all parts of business backing and advancement" including venture, the travel industry, R&D, and licensed innovation.⁷ It is significant in the present worldwide economy⁸ the worldwide monetary force has moved from created economies to rising economies. This thusly has made legislatures of created economies bolster national business which is engaged with the way toward internationalizing and growing across fringes.

1.2 THE BASIC DIMENSIONS BETWEEN COMMERCIAL DIPLOMACY AND INVESTMENT

There are generous contrasts between (national) CDC frameworks as for authoritative/institutional courses of action. The CD's unit position is at the focal point of authoritative concerns. The different sorts of recognizable plans fill in as a premise to expand the criteria concerning authoritative courses of action. Criteria, for example, the trade advancement associations of TPO relative autonomy, for example decentralization from services, its situation in the trade advancement structure, the mindful service, for business discretion are among the most significant. Government structures as far as capable services appear to be especially mind boggling, for example Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA) or/and Ministry of Trade (MT) and advancement offices (TPOs more often than not). There are various potential designs: now and again the MFA overwhelms, in others the MT, and some of the time even joint structures exist (UK). Additionally, there is a distinction in the TPO's situation in the structure and its association with the CD.

1.3 CHANGING MENTALITIES OF COMMERCIAL DIPLOMACY IN CHINA

The Chinese Commercial Diplomacy is based on production of elusive resources for example, data, picture, relationship capital and it depends on human resources (individuals' time and exertion). China's Commercial Diplomacy exercises are a way to arrive at government targets and furthermore to fulfill solid business requests, for example Compact discs look for the fulfillment of recipient business firms as well, as the "business advertiser" kind of CD appears to turn into the pattern. The accompanying exercises are ordinarily completed by CDs and, in this manner, their weight and angles are frequently unique in relation to other trade bolster establishments (TSIs). At the point when exercises are done most expertly in agreement with both government's destinations and recipient's fulfillment, at that point we consider that CDs really enhance the advancement of International Business (IB). Commercial-related elements of discretionary emissaries are obviously perceived under the Vienna Convention on political relations (Vienna Convention 1961 and consequent changes) – which unequivocally alludes to conciliatory exercises, for example, (i) assurance inside the host condition of the premiums of the home state and its nationals remembering their property and offers for organizations, (ii) gathering financial data, and (iii) advancement of monetary and logical relations between the two states, which incorporates business and speculation related issues (Vienna Convention 1961).

1.3.1 BACKGROUND AND SKILLS

Carron de la Carrière (1998), contends that business support is no activity for customary representatives; rather, the activity discovers its underlying foundations and difficulties in promoting, showcase information, business and money related systems which are all in all not anticipated from conventional vocation negotiators. The inquiry is real to the extent one asks: what do elevated level government trades (at a lawful system level) and nation positions at the International Monetary Fund and the World Trade Organization need to do straightforwardly with the advancement of business bargains and the advertising plan of a SME. The issue of enrolling the correct profile and capabilities remains. It is a test for governments to enlist possibly proficient CDs who are in a climbing profession stage.

1.3.2 STYLE/ORIENTATION

There are generous contrasts between (national) CDC frameworks as for their vision of what style of business strategy ought to be supported. Compact disc style doesn't just rely upon national parameters, and the way to deal with style can develop rapidly because of remote impact, CDs' experience and character for example. Recipients' association with government is firmly connected to CD style. The last develops perhaps out of (i) government conviction to act business agreeable and (ii) recipient weight and intrigue. The accompanying examples developed out of our observational research. A business advertiser might be portrayed as a business-arranged, star dynamic CD that looks for the fulfillment of organizations served (as opposed to that of the service). Their significant job is to give the consultancy-like administrations mentioned by business firms.

1.3.3 ACTIVITIES AND AREAS

CDC produces immaterial resources for example; data, picture, relationship capital and it depends on human resources (individuals' time and exertion). Cds complete exercises as a way to arrive at government destinations and furthermore to fulfill solid business requests, for example Compact discs look for the fulfillment of recipient business firms as well, as the "business advertiser" sort of CD appears to turn into the pattern. The accompanying exercises are normally done by CDs and, consequently, their weight and angles are regularly not the same as other trade bolster foundations (TSIs).

II. INSTITUTIONAL STRUCTURE OF CHINESE COMMERCIAL DIPLOMACY

In the everyday work the Nigeria Embassy in Beijing and the Consulates encourage various exercises focused for Commercial and the Nigerian authorities in China are profoundly associated with the acknowledgment of the technique points. It is consequently critical to think about these endeavors, which will be examined in the following area. The Chinese Commercial diplomacy can serve a national security purpose as trade stabilizes security threats because trade partners are less likely to enter war (Kopp, 2004). Despite the fact that commercial diplomacy focuses on trade relations it is important to emphasize the security agenda in utilizing commercial diplomacy, as it is largely acknowledged that trade partners avoid violent conflicts (Kopp, 2004). A nation's Commercial Diplomacy will vary from country to country as it is depending on characteristics of the home and the host country (Stadman and Ruël, 2012).

1.4 CHINA'S INTERESTS IN AFRICA

Political Interests: Since the beginning of the People's Republic of China, political interests have been the stay of and steady topic in Beijing's relationship with Africa. In its quest for companions in the bipolar Cold War worldwide framework,

Beijing distinguished Africa's recently free countries as a key gathering with which to join together. China saw regular shared belief and bore a feeling of sympathy with Africa because of their common verifiable encounters: Africa and China were the two survivors of "colonization by the entrepreneurs and settlers" and confronted a similar assignment of national freedom and freedom after World War II. Besides, as an individual from the communist camp, China saw the unbiased situation of most African nations among industrialist and communist coalitions as helpful for China's inclinations since Africa would be against the attack and war plans of the settlers.

Monetary Interests: There is a discussion inside China on whether political interests or monetary interests ought to speak to China's top need in its general Africa system. Chinese authorities have reliably underscored that, for most of the previous six decades, China's objective in Africa has never been the monetary advantages: In 2011, China's then-Premier Wen Jiabao gladly expressed that "China had magnanimously helped Africa when itself was the least fortunate. We didn't misuse one single drop of oil or concentrate one single ton of minerals out of Africa. This implies Beijing sees Africa first and most acutely through the viewpoint of political ties instead of monetary advantages.

Security Interests: Given the tremendous land separation, Africa presents barely any direct physical risk to China's prompt national security or the security of its outskirts. Be that as it may, as China's monetary exercises and work force nearness grow quickly on the landmass, the physical security of Chinese speculations and nationals has become the top test for Beijing. As per inadequate information, there are in any event 1 million Chinese living in Africa as of October 2012. These individuals are dependent upon various security dangers at the nearby level just as the state level because of the unpredictable political circumstances in Africa.

Ideological Interests: Historically, during the Cold War and before China's change and opening up, philosophy had been a fundamental factor deciding China's approach towards African nations. During this period, the foundation reasoning of China's approach towards Africa was that China ought to be the leader in the creating scene against expansionism, government and revisionism. The accentuation on belief system started from the unfriendly outside condition that constrained China to look for well-disposed discretionary space to guarantee its endurance. This philosophy driven arrangement brought about enormous guide to Africa notwithstanding China's own monetary troubles and was step by step relinquished after 1979. From that point forward, China no longer uses philosophy (socialism, communism or free enterprise) to decide its relationship to ideological groups and nations in Africa.

Economic Interests: China has organized and expanded its interests in Africa whereby both China and Africa have been joining forces on speculations for around the most recent eleven years. In September 2018, delegates from the two nations met at the seventh Forum on China-Africa Cooperation. The coordinated effort and participation makes Africa perhaps the best partner in the current worldwide market condition. The degree of China's interest in the mainland of Africa has been expanding at a consistent rate. At the 2018 China-Africa Cooperation Forum, China declared it would give \$60 billion in money related help to Africa. A portion of the essential inspirations that lie behind China's push toward expanded interests in African countries incorporate the longing to tie down a strong base of crude materials to fuel China's own quickly developing economy, the craving to build China's worldwide political impact, and the significant development opportunity introduced by developing business sector economies in Africa (Chika Onyejiuwa, 2018).

2. Concept of Diplomacy and Data Envelopment Analysis Method

In this section, the concept and classification of activity, Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) method and information about the models used will be given.

2.1 Descriptive Statistics

Trade:

The bilateral trade between China and Africa has been consistently expanding for as far back as 16 years. Nonetheless, poor costs of commodities since 2014 have extraordinarily affected value of items exported to China from Africa, even while Chinese exports to Africa stayed consistent. The estimation of China-Africa trade 2018 was \$185 bn, up from \$155 bn in 2017. In 2018, the biggest exporter to China from Africa was Angola, trailed by South Africa and The Republic of Congo. In 2018, South Africa was the biggest purchaser of Chinese merchandise, trailed by Nigeria and Egypt as illustrated in the figure 1 below; Sino-African trade is largely concentrated on a few countries and product groups. Africa focuses on the fare of characteristic assets where it has a turn imports work relative bit of leeway, and in serious fabricated products from China which is work plentiful. Strangely, South Africa's trade with China contrasts from that of other African nations as in both South African exports to and imports from China focus fundamentally on non-asset products. Although South Africa is one of the primary asset exporters to China, the portion of non-asset sends out in its all-out fares to China in 2012 was 72 percent.

Source: UN Comtrade, February 2020

Figure 1: Bilateral trade between China and Africa

In general, South Africa was China's most significant trading accomplice in non-asset products or non-resource goods (40 percent of all out Sino-African non-asset trade) and second most significant trading accomplice in asset merchandise or resource goods (16 percent of all out Sino-African asset trade), at side or of trade resources Angola plays an important role of (42 percent of all out Sino-African asset trade).

FDI:

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) is the net inflow of venture made to get an enduring administration enthusiasm for a business undertaking working in a nation other than that of the country investing. Such investments may appear as either "greenfield" venture - the securing and union of a current premium as opposed to new speculation (Moghalu, 2013). China's FDI in Africa is firmly connected to trade and improvement help. In this way FDI has expanded in the course of recent years couple with expanded Sino-African trade, in spite of the fact that China's FDI to Africa stays minor as far as China's all out outward FDI flows (0.2% in 1991 and 5.9% in 2007 Kaplinsky and Morris, 2009) and all out FDI got by Africa from the remainder of the world (3% in 2007). For the case of Chinese Ministry of Commerce, China's FDI in Africa has expanded by 46% every year throughout the most recent decade. The load of foreign investment remained at \$4.46 billion out of 2007 contrasted with \$56 million out of 1996. Throughout the first half of year 2009, Chinese FDI streams into Africa expanded by 81% contrasted with a similar period in 2008, coming to over \$0.5 billion. Nonetheless, it is difficult to be sure about the level of FDI outflow of China, as evaluations from various sources fluctuate broadly and Chinese investments are regularly directed through seaward substances enrolled in spots, for example, Hong Kong, Cayman Island and others.

Economic Relations

There has been support of economic cooperation projects in Africa by Government of China which frequently connects them with FDI and trade exercises further mirroring its political targets on the continent (Biggeri & Sanfilippo, 2009; Sanfilippo, 2010). Territories of monetary collaboration where China is generally dynamic in Africa incorporate foundation (railroads, streets, media transmission) and office development ventures (government structures, arenas, medical clinics, schools) (Bigger and Sanfilippo, 2009). Besides, China gives money related guide as awards, zero-premium advances, obligation alleviation, and concessional advances just as special fare credits, showcase rate trade purchasers' credits, and business advances from Chinese banks (Bräutigam, 2011). Moreover, the China Africa Development Fund propelled by the China Development Bank in 2007 gives value speculation cash-flow to Chinese ventures to put resources into Africa. The store has gotten \$3 billion in capital up until 2012 and has (co)financed 60 tasks across 30 African nations, and is relied upon to arrive at its full \$5 billion capitalization in 2014 (CCS, 2013) As the majority of China's Monetary Aid doesn't qualify as Official Development Assistance as characterized by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Development Assistance Committee, it is hard to contrast it and other givers' budgetary help. Besides, aside from a couple of authentic declarations remarking on major Sino-African ventures, there is an absence of complete authority Chinese guide information. All things considered, China distributes information on the turnover of financial collaboration projects. During the most recent decade Africa's offer in China's monetary participation worldwide has about significantly increased from 10% in 2000 to 29% in 2011 demonstrating the developing significance of China's activities in Africa as illustrated in Figure 3 below;

Figure 3: China's Economic Cooperation in Africa

In September, 2018 China set out on a monetary collaboration with various African nations whereby the china gave \$60 billion in type of budgetary help to Africa where the halfway dissemination of the assets was separated in type of: \$20 billion in credit lines, \$15 billion in awards, premium free advances and concessional advances, and \$10 billion in venture financing. This help will come as government help and venture. The venture plan drew analysis from savants expressing that it could trouble creating countries with impractical degrees of obligation. Consequently this as indicated by Figure 3 above, Chinese investment has expanded universally, and Africa is the third-biggest goal for Chinese speculation behind Asia and Europe. In any case, speculation toward sub-Saharan Africa somewhat declined in 2017, after the slight drop in total Chinese venture. Along these lines One-fourth of all Chinese investment is packed in Nigeria and Angola. Nigeria is one of China's biggest speculation accomplices on the continent; five of the \$60 billion promised at the 2015 FOCAC culmination were committed to Nigeria. As of late, Nigeria has gotten generally enormous assets from China for railway and road networks. China is supporting two significant standard-measure rail ventures: One is a line from Lagos to Kano; the other is a beach front railroad from Lagos to Calabar. The Nigerian government trusts that the last will bolster peacekeeping in the Niger Delta locale; in this way improving oil ventures there (oil is another key enthusiasm of China in Africa).

2.1.1 Commercial Diplomacy and FDI of China: Nigeria Case

Flows of Foreign direct investment (FDI) have been contended to be basic for financial thriving and supportability which has components of industrialization, work age, capital development, natural maintainability and monetary development among others (Liu, Hao, and Gao, 2017). FDI has a large group of preferences including growth of residential capital; move of innovation, information and abilities; advancement of rivalry and development; and upgrading send out execution. These must be weighed against different issues, for example, hostile to serious and prohibitive strategic approaches; charge shirking and oppressive exchange valuing; unstable progressions of venture and related installments injurious for equalization of installments; move of contaminating exercises and innovations; and over the top impact on financial issues with conceivable negative consequences for modern turn of events and national security. It is additionally kept up that the need to elevate the elements identified with effectiveness in utilization of elements of creation and their ensuing yields through moving of innovation advancement to creating financial matters must be accomplished through worldwide exchange with and the joining of FDI from created economies, individually (Alvarado, Iñiguez, and Ponce, 2017; Anwar and Nguyen, 2010).

Nigeria has huge assets, a large portion of which are yet to be completely misused. It has been accounted for that separated from oil, Nigeria's other normal assets incorporate petroleum gas, tin, iron mineral, coal, limestone, niobium, lead, zinc and arable land and are worth billions of dollars. There is no denying the way that gigantic open doors for outside direct speculation (FDI) exist in enterprises, for example, horticulture, normal assets, the travel industry, buyer merchandise, materials and amusement. Nigeria is the third host economy for FDI in Africa, behind Egypt and Ethiopia. The nation is among the most encouraging shafts of development in Africa and draws in various financial specialists in the area of hydrocarbon, vitality, structures and so forth. The nation experiences the impacts of the oil counter-stun. As indicated by the UNCTAD 2020 World Investment Report, FDI streams to Nigeria totalled to USD 3.3 billion of every 2019, demonstrating a 48,5% abatement contrasted with the earlier year (USD 6.4 billion out of 2018) under the impacts of gravity measures. The all out supply of FDI was assessed at USD 98,6 billion out of 2019.

A portion of the fundamental putting nations in Nigeria incorporate the USA, China, United Kingdom, the Netherlands and France. Nigeria plans to expand its economy away from oil by building a serious assembling segment, which ought to encourage incorporation into worldwide worth chains and lift profitability. The ongoing converging of exchange, industry and speculation under the ambit of the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment mirrors Nigeria's expectation to adequately facilitate between these three key territories to improve its exchanging and venture condition. A portion of the nation's primary favorable circumstances are a mostly privatized economy, a profitable tax collection framework, critical characteristic assets and an ease of work. Then again, far reaching defilement, political precariousness, absence of straightforwardness and low quality of foundation are restricting the nation's FDI potential. Serious administration additionally checks remote speculation.

Therefore, China has also been investing considerably in Nigeria, mainly in the textile, automotive and aerospace industries; whereby in **2017**, FDI Inward Flow was \$ 3,813(million USD), FDI Stock was \$ 88,917(million USD), a Number of Greenfield Investments was 36 and Value of Greenfield Investments (million USD) was at 4,841. **In 2018**, FDI Inward Flow (million USD) was at \$6,401, FDI Stock (million USD) was at \$95,318, Number of Greenfield Investments were at 57 and Value of Greenfield Investments (million USD) was at \$954, while in **2019**, FDI Inward Flow (million USD) was at \$3,299, FDI Stock (million USD) was at \$98,618, Number of Greenfield Investments were at 76 and Value of Greenfield Investments (million USD) was at \$10,196. This therefore implies that Nigeria has experienced a gradual increase in the level of investment from Nigeria mainly in the textile, automotive and aerospace industries between 2017 and 2019. This growth in investment levels has been attributed to Nigeria's strong points in terms of attracting which FDI include; the important size of its domestic market (Africa's most populous country), Nigeria possess Africa's highest GDP; it has important hydrocarbon resources and high agricultural potential; it has a relatively low public and external debt; and also the Nigerian Government's policy of economic liberalization, promoting public-private partnerships and strategic alliances with foreign companies have greater contributed to its gradual increase in attracting investments from China, as illustrated in table 1.1. Below;

Table 1.1foreign direct investments in Nigeria

Foreign Direct Investment	2017	2018	2019
FDI Inward Flow (million USD)	3,813	6,401	3,299
FDI Stock (million USD)	88,917	95,318	98,618
Number of Greenfield Investments***	36	57	76
Value of Greenfield Investments (million USD)	4,841	7,954	10,196

Source: UNCTAD - Latest available data.

Note: * The UNCTAD Inward FDI Performance Index is Based on a Ratio of the Country's Share in Global FDI Inflows and its Share in Global GDP. ** The UNCTAD Inward FDI Potential Index is based on 12 Economic and Structural Variables Such as GDP, Foreign Trade, FDI, Infrastructures, Energy Use, R&D, Education, and Country Risk. *** Green Field Investments Are a Form of Foreign Direct Investment Where a Parent Company Starts a New Venture in a Foreign Country By Constructing New Operational Facilities From the Ground Up. **** Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) Measures the Value of Additions to Fixed Assets Purchased By Business, Government and Households Less Disposals of Fixed Assets Sold Off or Scrapped.

The Nigerian Government has acquainted numerous projects with support FDI, strikingly in agribusiness, misuse and mining, oil and gas extraction, just as in the fare segments. Expense motivating forces are conceded to spearheading enterprises considered valuable for the monetary improvement of the nation and work of its workforce, (for example, dress); stipends encouraging capital ventures and the conclusion of enthusiasm on credits for gas organizations are likewise arranged.

4.1.2. Current Bilateral Trade Transactions between Nigeria and China **Trends analysis of Nigeria-China bilateral trade**

An investigation of trade stream information in Figure 4, uncovers the patterns in Nigeria-China respective trade relations of the two imports, fare and complete trade for the periods 1992-2018. Nigeria-China two-sided trade has stayed low particularly before the marking of a respective trade understanding between the two nations. Trade between the two nations has become fundamentally after the marking of reciprocal trade and speculation advancement and assurance understanding in 2001. Reciprocal trade between the two nations arrived at a top in 2014 with an all-out trade estimation of \$18.05 billion which declined to \$14.94 billion and \$10.62 billion out of 2015 and 2016. This declined in respective trade was because of ongoing government approach which planned for lessening importation of outside produced merchandise.

Figure 4: Trends in Nigeria-China Trade 1992-2018

Source: Author's Computation from UNCOMTRADE Statistics.

This affected a ton on Nigeria-China trade as most the purchaser merchandise in Nigeria was imported from China. Notwithstanding this, by and by now, China is Nigeria's significant wellspring of import, as imports from China hits \$13.7 billion of every 2015 however it declined to \$9.7 billion of every 2016. The expansion in China's fare to Nigeria is to the detriment of Nigeria's conventional exchanging accomplices like USA, Canada, and Europe. In 2014, very nearly fifteen years in the wake of consenting to trade arrangement among Nigeria and China, two-sided trade expanded right around multiple times its incentive before consenting to trade arrangement 2001.

All through the investigation time frames, Nigeria imports a larger number of products than it fares to China. The connection among Nigeria and China had developed nearer because of universal segregation and judgment of Nigeria's military systems 1970-1998. While then again, the Chinese open entryway strategy set out by the socialist party in 1978 drove by Deng Xiaoping which gives equivalent business and modern rights to all the nationals additionally encouraged or hurried the financial relations between the two nations.

Ogunkola, Bankole and Adewuyi (2008) took a brief perspective on Nigeria-China relations and expressed that: Nigeria's connection with China has bloomed as of late. This connection represented by understandings, conventions and settlements spread over a range of regions including political, trade, venture, help, specialized, logical, social, training, wellbeing and military. The usage of these understandings gave off an impression of being disproportionate as China is by all accounts on the road to success while Nigeria has all the earmarks of being slacking behind. Thus, right now bilateral trade has developed exponentially since China and Nigeria consented to an arrangement on trade and venture advancement and security in 2001. The estimation of trade came to USD 17.7 billion of every 2010, right around multiple times its level only ten years prior while Nigerian fares to China dramatically increased, they have not stayed up with the development of Chinese fares to Nigeria. In this way a substantial trade irregularity has endured as well as heightened. Chinese fares spoke to 66.7% of the respective trade all out 2000 and 87.3% of the aggregate in 2010. By 2010, Nigeria had become China's fourth greatest Africa exchanging accomplice, and the second biggest Chinese fare goal on the landmass. Trade between the two nations represented about 33% of the trade among China and the entire of West Africa, demonstrating the significance of Nigeria to China's entrance into the local market. Regardless of late extension,

Table 1.2: Nigeria's Largest Import Partners & Nigeria's Largest Export Destination

Country	% of Total	GDP Rate	COUNTRY	% of Total	GDP Rate
China	16.0	6.90	India	16.8	5.7
Belgium	12.3	1.50	Spain	12.1	3.10
Netherlands	9.7	3.30	USA	10.2	2.2
USA	7.5	2.2	Netherlands	7.8	3.30
Italy	6.2	1.5	France	7.2	1.70

Source: National Bureau of Statistics, September, 2017

China still just records for a little portion of Nigeria's worldwide trade, lingering a long ways behind the nation's top accomplice (the United States) and furthermore remarkably confronting rivalry from Brazil and India, just as progressively conventional accomplices, for example, France. An investigation of trade stream information in Figure 4, uncovers the patterns in Nigeria-China respective trade relations of the two imports, fare and complete trade for the periods 1992-2018. Nigeria-China two-sided trade has stayed low particularly before the marking of a respective trade understanding between the two nations. Trade between the two nations has become fundamentally after the marking of reciprocal trade and speculation advancement and assurance understanding in 2001. Reciprocal trade between the two nations arrived at a top in 2014 with an all-out trade estimation of \$18.05 billion which declined to \$14.94 billion and \$10.62 billion out of 2015 and 2016. This declined in respective trade was because of ongoing government approach which planned for lessening importation of outside produced merchandise. The table 1.2 above shows negative equalization of trade against Nigeria for China. In 1999, the trade trades between the two nations indicated trade difference of 29,219,066,770 where Nigeria just sent out merchandise worth 10,671,356,489 to China and that equivalent period, Nigeria imported products from China worth 39,890,423,259. In 2008, the trade lopsidedness likewise shows 470,948,778,909 for China. Nigeria is just observed as completed items goal for China. She considers Nigeria to be a decent market for her merchandise.

Trends in Balance of Trade (1992-2018)

Source: Author's Computation from UNCOMTRADE Statistics

Nigeria's fare to China has not stayed up with its import as appeared in Figure 5. Consequently, there was never be a trade balance favor of Nigeria and this trade unevenness has kept on expanding as well as increased. All through the investigation time frame, Nigeria's import from China spoke to at least 64.10% of the two-sided complete trade. In 1993, of the absolute trade recorded, Nigeria's import from China spoke to over 99% with less than 1% speaking to its fare offer to China.

Trends in the growth of Import, Export, Total Trade and balance of trade 1992-2018

Source: Author's Computation from UNCOMTRADE Statistics

Figure 6: Trends in the growth of import, export, total trade and balance of trade 1992-2018

This is an away from of trade balance been supportive of the Chinese economy. There was no improvement recorded subsequent to consenting to a respective trade arrangement as the portion of Nigeria's fares to its all-out trade with China exacerbated with a declined from 19.85% in 2001 to 8.51% in 2018. This upheld the outcome got by (Ayoola, 2013).

Figure 6, delineates the patterns in the development of import, send out, absolute trade, and trade offset of Nigeria's trade with China over the investigation time frames 1992-2018. In view of the development information and as apparent from figure 10, Nigeria's trade with China encountered a blast from 1992-2018 in spite of the rising and falling patterns all through the periods. The most noteworthy fare development was recorded in 1995 which was a consequence of huge change in mineral energizes trade as the item rules Nigeria's fare to China as well as to the remainder of the world. Trade balance develops drastically between the years 1995-1997 and 2000-2001. This gigantic development in the trade balance is likewise reflected in the variety among fares and import to and from China which was, accordingly, high import request of Chinese merchandise by Nigerian with little fare gracefully to China to coordinate with expanding import. The development in trade balance has since 2013 ceaselessly declining and even turns negative in 2015 and 2018. This was because of the nations having to support its fare flexibly to China as well as to the world when all is said in done.

III. CONCLUSION

Nigeria-China bilateral trade Nigeria-China two-sided trade has stayed low particularly before the consenting to two-sided trade arrangement. Trade between the two nations has developed essentially in the wake of marking reciprocal trade, venture advancement and security understanding in 2001. Regardless of the ongoing decrease in reciprocal trade, the current respective trade has outperformed the earlier decades' two-sided trade terms of size, effect, and pertinence to the two economies. The examination demonstrates that Nigeria's fare to China has not stayed up with its import from China as there was never be a parity of trade favor of Nigeria and this trade unevenness has kept on expanding as well as heightened. All through the investigation time frame, Nigeria's import from China spoke to at the very least 64.10% of the absolute reciprocal trade. The patterns development uncovers the most noteworthy fare development in 1995 which was the consequence of huge change in mineral energizes send out as this item commands Nigeria's fare to China as well as to the remainder of the world. The development in trade balance has since 2013 constantly declining and even turns negative in 2015 and 2018. This was because of the nations having to support its fare flexibly to China as well as to the world as a rule. Of all the significant items sent out, mineral fills and result of their refining represents the biggest portion of 83% and rules the absolute fare in the entire time frames 1992-2018. This suggests over the investigation time frame fare to China was less expanded contrasted with import from China. The examination further presumes that, taking a gander at the trade records the reciprocal trade between the two nations has been agreeable to China than Nigeria. All through the investigation time frame, Nigeria's fare force has not been improved, suggesting that fare to China has not been differentiated. Taking a gander at the Nigeria-China trade synthesis, the investigation suggests an earnest requirement for Nigeria's administration to empower the fare of different items so as to advance reciprocal trade and relieve the current trade irregularity. Considering the low fare force controlled by Nigeria, there is a requirement for government, scientists, and fare advancement offices to recognize new open doors for Nigeria's fares in the Chinese market. This will help in broadening Nigeria's fare and reinforce trade relations between the nations. There is additionally a requirement for government and scientists to recognize boundaries looked by Nigeria's fare to China as far as a functioning reciprocal trade understanding, levy and non-tax hindrances.

The trade among Nigeria and China has to a great extent followed an old style example of trade disequilibrium between the creating and the created economies. The structure of trade among Nigeria and China mirrors the distinction in the degree of advancement of the two accomplices just as high level of complementarities that exist between their economies. While Nigeria's fares to China comprise for the most part of essential products, its imports from that nation are comprised of generally of mechanical merchandise. Inside these product gatherings, there have been some significant changes in the structure of trade throughout the years.

REFERENCES

1. Adekola, O.G. (2013). New perspective to Nigeria's foreign policy towards China, IOSR journal of humanities and social science, 6 (5), 01-06
2. Akeem, U.O. (2011), Performance evaluation of foreign trade and economic growth in nigeria, Journal of Finance and Accounting vol.2, No 2, 2222-2847
3. Alexandre Mercier, (2007). 'Commercial diplomacy in advanced industrial states', Discussion Papers in Diplomacy, No. 108 (The Hague: Netherlands Institute of International Relations 'Clingendael',
4. Asongu, S. A., & Aminkeng, G. A. A., (2013). "The economic consequences of China-Africa relations: debunking myths in the debate", Journal of Chinese Economic and Business Studies, 11(4), pp. 261-277.

5. Breinlich, H., Mion, G., Nolan, P. and D. Novy (2012), "Intellectual Property, Overseas Sales, and the Impact of UKTI Assistance in Entering New Overseas Markets", Report to UKTI.
6. Carmody, P., & Owusu, F., (2007). "Chinese vs. America geoeconomic strategies in Africa", *Political Geography*, *Political Geography*, 26, pp. 504-524.
7. Dayo Aiyetan, (2010). "How China Fuels Deforestation In Nigeria, West Africa," International Centre for Investigative Reporting (Nigeria),
8. Garten J., Zoellick R., Shinn J. (1998), *Riding the Tigers: American Commercial Diplomacy in Asia*, Columbia International Affairs online, Columbia University Press,
9. Harris R. and Li Q. (2005). *Review of Literature: Review of the Literature: The Role of International Trade and Investment in Business Growth and Development*, United Kingdom of Great Britain, Richard Harris & Q. Cher Li (copyright).
10. Helmers C., Rogers, M. and P. Schautschick (2011), "Intellectual Property at the Firm-Level in the UK", Oxford University, Department of Economics Working Paper No. 546.
11. Kopp, Harry W., (2004), *Commercial Diplomacy and the National Interest*, American Academy of Diplomacy/ Business Council for International Understanding
12. Kosteci M., Brossard H., Furrer O. Gramigna M. (1994) *L'image des services suisses: Enjeux et proposition d'action*, *Die Unternehmung*, Zurich, 1/94, 35-50.
13. Kotabe, M., and Czinkota, M. R. (1992). "State government promotion of manufacturing exports: A gap analysis", *Journal of International Business Studies*, 23(4), 637-658.
14. Maaïke Okano-Heijmans (2010). 'Hantering van het begrip economische diplomatie', *Internationale Spectator*, Vol. 64, No. 5 pp. 73-74; Maaïke Okano-Heijmans and Huub Ruel, 'Commerciële diplomatie en internationaal ondernemen', *Internationale Spectator*, Vol. 65, No. 9 (2011).
15. Michel Kosteci and Olivier Naray (2007). 'Commercial diplomacy and international business', *Discussion Papers in Diplomacy*, No. 107 (The Hague: Netherlands Institute of International Relations 'Clingendael',
16. Naray, O. (2008). *Commercial Diplomacy: A Conceptual Overview*." Conference paper for the 7th World Conference of TPOs – The Hague, The Netherlands.
17. Naray, O. (2010). *What a good Commercial Diplomat has to know and be capable of*, *Exchange: The Magazine for International Business and Diplomacy*, 2 (December 2010): 8-9.
18. Ogunkola, A. S. Bankole and A. Adewuyi, (2008), *China-Nigeria economic relations: AERC scoping studies on China-Africa relations, a revised report submitted to the Africa economic research consortium (AERC)*, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria, 2008, 3-16
19. Reuvers, S. and Ruel, H. J. M., (2012). "Research on Commercial Diplomacy: Review and Implications" in *Commercial Diplomacy and International Business: a conceptual and empirical exploration*, Ruel, H. J. M., ed. (Advanced series in Management, Emerald,
20. Ruel, H. J. M. and Visser, R. (2012). *Commercial Diplomats as corporate entrepreneurs: explaining role behavior from an institutional perspective*", *International Journal of Diplomacy and Economy*.
21. Saner R. and Yiu L. (2003), *International economic diplomacy: Mutations in post-modern times*, *Discussion Papers in Diplomacy*, 84, The Hague, Clingendael Institute.
22. Taylor, I., (2007). "Governance in Africa and Sino-Africa Relations: Contradictions or Confluence?", *Politics*, 27(3), pp. 139-146.
23. Utomi, P. (2012). *China and Nigeria*, , retrieved from http://080603_utomi_nigeriachina, September 2013